

Year 2: Publishable Summary

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<http://www.3dicons-project.eu>

Project objectives

The 3D-ICONS project started in February 2012 and has completed its second year with one year left to go. The project focuses on digital content that includes 3D models and reconstructions, enlarged models of important details and related images, texts and videos. It will also include and re-contextualize in 3D, objects belonging to a monument but presently located elsewhere, for example in museums. The project's activities predominantly consist of new digitisations but also includes some existing 3D data, all of which is being converted into formats accessible by Europeana users. 3D-ICONS is expected to make a significant impact by providing Europeana with an unprecedented quantity of high-quality, 3D, well-organized and attractive information about the masterpieces of European architecture and archaeology.

The project aims to complement the collections which have been made available to Europeana via CARARE, Europeana Local, Athena and other projects which have developed the content base for the architectural and archaeological heritage. Most notably, the results of 3D-ICONS will complement the 3D models brought to Europeana via the CARARE project and to increase the critical mass of this engaging content. It is also an important objective to build on the results of previous EU projects, most notably on CARARE, for the aggregation services and guidelines on the publication of 3D for Europeana, and on 3D-COFORM for the 3D creation, management and visualization tools.

The target users of the 3D-ICONS include:

- members of the general public, tourists and students who wish to be able to explore and enjoy architectural and archaeological masterpieces which are often inaccessible to visitors either as a result of their remote locations or because conservation management restricts access to only parts of the monuments.
- Europeana users who wish to access, explore and enjoy 3D models together with the related high-quality information.
- The cultural institutions who are in charge of internationally and nationally important monuments and buildings and who need tried and tested mechanisms to produce high quality 3D documentation and publish the results for Europeana as well as on their own websites.
- UNESCO and cultural institutions wishing to find new ways of delivering their missions to promote understanding and increase the sustainability of world and European heritage.
- Content providers and creative industry SMEs wishing to identify sustainable business processes and models.

3D-ICONS will both contribute to the expansion of Europeana's content base and also offer enhanced experiences for its users by bringing exciting and engaging content for archaeological monuments and historic buildings. This content will comprise of a range of formats including 3D models, movies, texts and 2D images.

Progress during Year 2 (February 2013 – January 2014)

Laser scanning platform, Skellig Michael

During the second year, the project partners are well into digitising the selected sites and monuments which has meant trips to remote areas and archaeological sites of great importance.

One of these was Skellig Michael, a monastic settlement of stone beehive structures on a remote island abandoned around the 12th century and only accessible by boat during the summer months off the west coast of Ireland. Other sites include a Neolithic temple at Puente Tablas in Andalusia and the Holy Well of St. Cristina in Sardinia. As expected, there have been some IPR issues which have been mainly resolved by the substitution of alternative sites.

One of the benefits of participating in European Projects is transfer of knowledge between partners, enabling those newer to 3D technologies to improve their skills and the quality of their acquired datasets and resulting models.

To this end, some of the partners have participated in training workshops to learn about the latest acquisition and modelling techniques such as the use of UAVs and photogrammetry. One partner, MNIR of Romania, organised a national training event for other cultural heritage institutions following their attendance at a 3D summer school organised by partner FBK. The project also organised two internal metadata training workshops and a very successful technical workshop describing the different models and techniques adopted by partners at the Digital Heritage Conference hosted in Marseilles at the end of October 2013.

UAV "Octo-copter" used by Athena-RC

In order to support the complete 3D model creation process, there have also been significant developments in the infrastructure and tools. At the end of the first year, the CARARE2 metadata schema was published, having been updated to include 'paradata' that is specific to 3D models (e.g. dataset type, processing method, equipment and settings used, final formats). 3D-ICONS will be using the same infrastructure as CARARE adapted to the new schema for storage and ingestion to Europeana but it was also realised that a simple metadata editing tool would greatly speed up the creation of the required metadata and assist the less experienced partners in addition to providing a valuable facility for newcomers wishing to use the 3D-ICONS pipeline. Consequently, a new Metadata Editor has been developed which has the advantages of creating reusable templates for each end user and outputting CARARE2 compliant XML files for ingestion into MoRE2.

At month 18, the project published a report on IPR Schemes which described the various licensing scenarios and possible solutions. It appears that Europeana's adoption of the Creative Commons licensing framework along with other prominent initiatives such as WikiLovesMonuments is having a positive impact in that this is making digital content owners pay more attention to IPR whilst also enabling them to open up access to their collections. This change in attitude was evidenced in 3D-ICONS where more organisations have started to use Creative Commons for licensing since the start of the project. One of the objectives of 3D-ICONS is to demonstrate best practice in dealing with IPR for making 3D models available through Europeana and the 3D-ICONS portal.

Example of visual enrichment based on the projection of textures starting from photographs finely oriented on the 3D model (CNRS-MAP)

During this period, the project has also focussed upon post-processing and publication formats that are suitable for Europeana end users, publishing two reports at M21 which addressed these technical topics. The deliverable “D4.1 Interim report on Post-processing” provides an overview of the main steps comprising this activity: geometric reconstruction, visual enrichment, model structuring and hypothetical reconstruction. Four case studies from the partners illustrate the variety of approaches used.

The deliverable “D5.1 Publication Formats Suitable for Europeana” discusses the 3D requirements of Europeana and the challenges posed by complex 3D models.

A wide range of currently available technologies are presented with pros and cons, followed by recommendations for 3D-ICONS. At present, the most suitable formats are 3D-PDF for objects of low complexity (e.g. museum objects), HTML5/WebGL for objects and highly complex point cloud models, Unity3D/UnReal for less complex buildings and sites and the more complex ones where the level of detail can be optimised; and Pseudo 3D is also an option for highly complex models across the board. At this point in time, it is likely that the Nexus-based Community Presenter which employs web-streaming for complex 3D models will be a favoured option along with 3D-PDF with some examples of the other formats. It should be noted that with the current rapid changes in 3D viewing technologies, other options may become available.

Finally, project has been widely disseminated through social media, conferences, journals and other channels:

- More than two international events have been organised,
- Partners have delivered more than 26 presentations at international conferences,
- Twenty seven articles have been published in conference proceedings and academic journals,
- The project website has received more than 12,500 visits,
- Project news and the newsletter are being read by more than 200 people.
- Articles about the project have been published in national newspapers in Spain, Ireland, the UK and Greece,

- The project has established external partner agreements with four organisations who wish to make their 3D models available to Europeana and also learn about a metadata schema suitable for their datasets.

Main results achieved

The main results achieved to date are:

- Over 60% of the current inventory of monuments and buildings has been digitized,
- An online Metadata Editor tool which enables users to create re-usable templates based on CARARE 2.0, has been developed for general use,
- All content providing partners have now signed Europeana Data Exchange Agreement bringing the total to thirteen,
- Dissemination activities have accelerated with many articles and papers published, presentations at conferences and a well-attended technical workshop at Digital Heritage, Marseilles 2013.
- Deliverables addressing Post-processing (D4.1), Publication formats (D5.1), Metadata creation (D4.2), Data acquisition (D3.1) and updated versions of the IPR Schema (D7.2) and Dissemination Plan (D8.2) have been published.

Expected final results and potential impact

By the end of the project, 3D-ICONS will provide a tried and tested process for the conversion and production of 3D content and the associated information which includes the technology and tools, a metadata schema tailored for 3D models, best practice guidelines and wide expertise built on many years of partner experience. This will enable other cultural heritage owners of 3D content to likewise contribute their models to Europeana, raising awareness and increasing the knowledge base of all the identified stakeholders. The high quality models will also be available for other potential users; there have been expressions of interest by researchers (archaeologists, architects, restorers) in use of the 3D models and the Metadata schema and this is expected, for example, to lead to further cooperation agreements with other projects and organisations. This process along with other additional information about 3D models such as different formats available, associated IPR and other options for viewing the models will be made available on the 3D-ICONS portal.

End users of Europeana will be able to search and find several thousand high quality 3D models of historic buildings and monuments, archaeological sites and related items and view these on standard computers and mobile devices. Through 3D models, the general public can visit sites which may be in remote locations, fragile and, in some cases, difficult to understand. 3D models can be enjoyed by a wide range of end users with an interest in cultural heritage, for educational purposes and to engage and enthuse people about archaeology and architecture, raising the profile of the institutions such as museums providing access and knowledge within this sector across Europe.

***Bronze Roman Bust
Archaeological Museum, Milan
(POLIMI)***

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